

PHARMACEUTICALS

EXTRACTION PROCESS AND ACUTE TOXICITY OF A SUBSTANCE BASED ON BIOLOGICALLY ACTIVE POLYSACCHARIDES FROM THE ROOT OF *CAPPARIS SPINOSA*

Botirov R.,

PhD, Institute chemistry of plant substances Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Saidova G.,

Basic doctoral student researcher of the Experimental and Technological Laboratory of the ICPS AS.Uz

Azamatov A.,

PhD, Institute chemistry of plant substances Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Akhmadjonov K.,

Institute of Chemistry of Plant Substances, Uzbekistan

Khalilov R.

doctor of technical Sciences,

Institute of Chemistry of Plant Substances, Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10054623>

Abstract

The article discusses the main factors in the process of extracting a substance based on water-soluble biologically active polysaccharides from the root of the *Capparis spinosa* plant - the degree of grinding of the raw material, the effect of the extractant, the influence of factors such as the influence of temperature and time on the extraction process, as well as the water-soluble substance from the root of the *Capparis spinosa* plant and the acute toxicity of total polysaccharides were studied in laboratory animals.

Keywords: *Capparis spinosa* - capers, raw materials, extraction, solvent, concentration, temperature, polysaccharides, technology, acute toxicity.

Introduction.

Capparis spinosa are a perennial medicinal plant that grows wild in our country. Distributed throughout Central Asia, including all rocky, low-mountain, desert and hilly regions of Uzbekistan. A number of scientific studies have been conducted to study the pharmacotoxicological and biological properties of *Capparis spinosa* [1-9]. The above-ground part of this plant can be harvested in large quantities per year without harming its natural reserves. *Capparis spinosa* contain 0.12-0.15% ascorbic acid, 0.32-0.44% flavonoids, 23-29% nitrogenous compounds, 3.5-4.2% fatty substances, 1.2% pectins and glycosides, coumarins, carbohydrates. Scientists at the Institute of Plant Chemistry conducted research on lipids and carbohydrates [11-14] contained in the root [10], seeds and leaves of *Capparis spinosa*.

Capparis spinosa are widely used in folk medicine to treat various diseases. Abu Ali ibn Sina used *Capparis spinosa* as an anesthetic, in the treatment of wounds and injuries, asthma, and gastrointestinal diseases. A decoction of the root is used to treat hepatitis, smoke from the rhizomes is used to treat syphilis, and a tincture of the fruit is used to treat hemorrhoids, dental diseases and to strengthen the gums [15,16]. The hepatoprotective drug Liv 52, produced in India, contains caper extract [17]. According to information from the literature, caper root has not been sufficiently studied chemically. Therefore, research is being carried out widely to determine the amount of carbohydrates in caper root.

Purpose of the study.

Study of factors influencing the extraction process when developing technology for extracting biologically active substances from plant materials. The XI State Pharmacopoeia describes the development of a technology for extracting the amount of water-soluble polysaccharides from caper root, as well as determining the amount of water-soluble polysaccharides in plant materials and the quantitative proportion of polysaccharides, studying the acute toxicity of the amount of polysaccharides carried out in the department of pharmacology and toxicology of our institute.

Materials and methods. After determining the total amount of water-soluble polysaccharides in plant raw materials, studies were carried out on their highly productive extraction from raw materials. To this end, continuing our research, we conducted research to study the effectiveness of factors affecting the extraction process, namely: the degree of grinding of raw materials, the type and concentration of solvent, temperature and duration of extraction and determining the frequency of extraction of raw materials. During the experiments, the total yield of polysaccharides was determined by analytical analysis. Therefore, an analytical sample of 10 g (exact weight) of the raw material, consisting of caper root, was taken, placed in a ground-bottom round flask with a capacity of 250 ml, 200 ml of water was poured into the flask, a reflux refrigerator was connected to the flask and boiled on an electric stove for 30 minutes with stirring. The extraction was repeated two more times: 1st time with 200 ml, 2nd time with 100 ml of water. The aqueous extracts were combined and centrifuged at

5000 rpm for 10 min. Then we took a flask with a capacity of 500 ml, placed a glass funnel with a diameter of 55 mm on the neck, inserted a 5-layer gauze cloth moistened with water onto the funnel, and filtered the extracts from the centrifuge through the gauze. The filter was washed with water and filled with water until the volume of the solution reached the scale mark (Solution A).

We took 25 ml of solution A and placed it in a centrifuge cup, 75 ml of 95% ethyl alcohol was added to the cup, mixed thoroughly, placed in a water bath, heated for 5 minutes at a temperature of 30 °C and left for 1 hour. After the specified period, it was placed in a centrifuge and rotated for 30 minutes at a speed of 5000 rpm. The liquid part in the glass was separated and dried to a constant weight at a temperature of 100-105 °C, and the residue was filtered through a glass filter with a diameter of 40 mm and a 16-hole hole size under vacuum at a pressure of 13-16 kPa. The precipitate was filtered repeatedly and washed first in 15 ml of an aqueous mixture of 95% ethyl alcohol (3:1), then in 10 ml of acetone and 10 ml of ethyl acetate. The precipitate that fell on the filter was first dried in the open air, then at a temperature of 100-105 °C until a constant mass was formed.

The amount of polysaccharides in plant raw materials (X) was calculated using the following formula, taking into account the content of absolutely dry raw materials:

$$X = \frac{(m_2 - m_1) \cdot 500 \cdot 100 \cdot 100}{m \cdot 25 \cdot (100 - W)}$$

where m_1 – filter mass in grams,

m_2 – mass of the filter including sediment in grams,

m – mass of raw materials in grams,

W – weight loss of raw materials during drying as a percentage.

Depending on different growing seasons and the location of caper growth, the amount of water-soluble polysaccharides in the samples ranged from 0.6% to 1.1%.

Assessment of acute toxicity of the sum of water-soluble polysaccharides from the root of the *Capparis spinosa* plant. To conduct the experiments, sterile white male mice weighing 18-20 g, taken from a special nursery “Linear Experimental Animals” in the Tashkent region, were kept under standard vivarium conditions with 12-hour lighting and an air temperature of 20±2°C. Feeding was carried out in accordance with the nutritional standard for experimental animals, and unlimited access to water was provided. The experiments were carried out on outbred white mice kept under standard vivarium conditions in accordance with the rules adopted by the “European Convention for the Protection of Vertebrate Animals Used for Experimental or Other Scientific Purposes” ETS N 123 (Strasbourg, March 18, 1986) [18] . The amount of water-soluble polysaccharides from the root of the *Capparis spinosa* plant was administered in doses from 100.0 to 10,000.0 mg/kg into the stomach through the oral cavity using an atraumatic probe. Each dose was tested on 6 mice. The selection of doses and route of administration of substances was carried out in accordance with the “Guidelines for experimental (preclinical) studies of new pharmacological compounds” [19]. All experimental animals were continuously monitored for 14 days after the animals were administered the test compounds at the indicated doses. The semi-lethal dose (LD₅₀) was determined according to the method of Litchfield and Wilcoxon [20].

The results obtained and their discussion . To study the degree of effective grinding of raw materials, caper root was crushed (the amount of the sum of water-soluble polysaccharides compared to the dry weight of the raw material 0.6%) to a size of less than 3 mm, 4-7 mm and 8-12 mm. 0.5 kg of uncrushed raw material was placed in the first extractor, crushed to 8-12 mm in the second, crushed to 8-12 mm in the third, and up to 3 mm in the fourth.

The extractors were filled with water at room temperature until the raw materials were completely covered and after 8 hours the first discharge was taken. This process was repeated 7 times. The results are presented below in Table 1.

Table 1

The influence of the degree of grinding of raw materials on the yield of the amount of water-soluble polysaccharides from *Capparis spinosa* root

No.	Degree of grinding, mm	Yield of extractives relative to the mass of raw materials (%)	Yield of total water-soluble polysaccharides , %	
			Relative to the mass of raw materials	Depending on the amount of raw material reserves
1	Unground	20.2	0.35	58.3
2	8 – 12	21.3	0.41	68.3
3	4-7	24.2	0.45	75.0
4	Less than 3mm	21.1	0.48	80.0

From Table 1 it can be seen that when extracting from raw materials crushed to 3 mm, the filtration process becomes more complicated due to the large amount of polysaccharides soluble in the main water, as well as the turbidity of the extract and the large amount of dissolved extractives. As a result, a number of difficulties arise in the process of extracting the amount of water-soluble polysaccharides . When extracting from unground raw materials, the extraction

process is very slow and as a result, the extraction process takes a long time. It has been determined that in order to extract water-soluble polysaccharides with maximum yield, it is advisable to grind the raw material to a particle size of 4-7 mm.

After studying the degree of grinding of plant raw materials, a series of experiments were carried out to select an effective solvent for extracting raw materials. Organic solvents and their aqueous solutions were used

to carry out the experiments. The experiments were carried out under the same conditions and by extracting the same raw material samples with different solvents.

Weighing 0.5 kg of dry raw material, crushed to 4-7 mm, placed in 8 extractors with a capacity of 5 liters. Water was poured into the first extractor, ethyl alcohol (95 %) was poured into the 2nd, and 80, 70, 60, 50, 40% aqueous-alcohol solutions were poured into the 3, 4, 5, 6, 7th. Extractants were poured into all extractors until the raw materials were completely covered and

extraction was carried out by infusion at room temperature 6 times for 8 hours. All extracted alcoholic extracts were concentrated on a rotary evaporator to obtain an aqueous extract. The aqueous extract was concentrated until 1/10 remained. The total amount of water-soluble polysaccharides in the concentrated aqueous fraction was determined according to the method described above. The results of the experiments are presented below in Table 2.

Table 2

The influence of solvents on the yield of the amount of water-soluble polysaccharides from *Capparis spinosa* root

No.	Solvent	Yield of extractives relative to the mass of raw materials (%)	Yield of total water-soluble polysaccharides, %	
			Relative to the mass of raw materials	Depending on the amount of raw material reserves
1	Ethanol: 95%	10.1	0.10	16.7
2	80 %	14.2	0.13	21.7
3	70 %	16.5	0.18	30.0
4	60 %	18.6	0.23	38.3
5	50 %	19.2	0.30	50.0
6	40%	20.1	0.38	63.3
7	Water	25.2	0.45	75.0

From Table 2 it can be seen that when extracted with 95% concentrated ethyl alcohol, the smallest amount of water-soluble polysaccharides is released into the extract. With an increase in the amount of water in the aqueous-alcoholic solvent, the transfer of water-soluble polysaccharides into the extract increases, and it has been established that water-soluble polysaccharides are transferred into the extract with an efficiency of 85.0% when extracting with water, as the most effective extractant method.

When extracting biologically active substances from raw materials, the influence of temperature on the extraction process is also important. An increase in temperature increases the solubility of substances in the solvent and accelerates the process of transfer of substances from the raw material to the solvent. We have conducted a number of studies to study the effect of temperature on the process of extraction of water-soluble polysaccharides from raw materials.

From the dry raw material, the degree of grinding of which was 4-7 mm, 0.5 kg was weighed out, placed in 4 flasks and filled with an aqueous solvent until the raw material was completely covered. For the extraction process, the temperature in the first flask was controlled - maintained at 20-30 °C, in the second - 40-50 °C, in the third - 40-50 °C, and in the fourth - 50-60 °C (in an ITZh brand water thermostat -0-03, Russia).

The extraction process was carried out 8 times for 8 hours using the infusion method. All extracted alcoholic extracts were concentrated on a rotary evaporator to obtain an aqueous extract. The aqueous extract was concentrated until 1/10 remained. The total amount of water-soluble polysaccharides in the concentrated aqueous fraction was determined according to the method described above. The results of the studies are presented in Table 3.

Table 3

Effect of temperature on the yield of total water-soluble polysaccharides from *Capparis spinosa* root

No.	Temperature, °C	Yield of extractives relative to the mass of raw materials (%)	Yield of total water-soluble polysaccharides, %	
			Relative to the mass of raw materials	Depending on the amount of raw material reserves
1	20-30	20.2	0.42	70.0
2	30-40	25.7	0.47	78.3
3	40-50	27.0	0.51	85.0
4	50-60	28.2	0.55	91.7
5	60-70	28.2	0.56	93.3

From Table 3 it can be seen that increasing the temperature during the extraction of raw materials has a great influence on the extraction process of the amount of water-soluble polysaccharides. As the temperature increases, the amount of water-soluble polysaccharides dissolves in the extractant and the yield increases. Even at a temperature of 70 °C, the yield of water-soluble polysaccharides during the extraction

process turned out to be almost the same as at a temperature of 60 °C. Thus, we have established that during the process of water extraction of caper root, it is most effective to maintain the temperature within 50-60 °C.

We conducted a series of experiments to determine how many times the raw material should be extracted in order to extract the amount of water-soluble polysaccharides with the greatest yield. To do this, 0.5 kg was

weighed out of dry raw materials, the degree of grinding of which was 4-7 mm, placed in 4 flasks and filled with an aqueous solvent until the raw materials were completely covered. Room temperature maintained at

50-60°C and drained 8 hours after pouring the extractant. Each of the resulting aqueous extracts was analyzed by the above analytical methods. For this purpose, the result of our experiments is presented in Graph 1.

Schedule 1

The influence of the multiplicity of extractions on the yield of the amount of water-soluble polysaccharides from *Capparis spinosa* root

From Graph 1 it is clear that it is advisable to extract the raw material 5 times. We remove the last 5th drain for further extraction of raw materials.

During the extraction process, we conducted the following experiment to determine how much time should be spent obtaining each drain. To do this, 0.5 kg was weighed out of dry raw materials, the degree of grinding of which was 4-7 mm, placed in 4 flasks and filled

with an aqueous solvent until the raw materials were completely covered. Temperature in the extractor during the extraction process maintained a value of 60°C. The drain from 1 flask was poured out after 2 hours, 2 flasks after 4 hours, 3 flasks after 6 hours and 4 flasks after 8 hours. This process was continued until 5 drains were obtained. The experimental results are presented in Table 4.

Table 4

The influence of the time of obtaining plums on the yield of the amount of water-soluble polysaccharides from *Capparis spinosa* root , %

No.	1-drain	2-drain	3-drain	4-drain	5-drain	Time
1	29	13	5	2	1	2 hours
2	43	20	8	4	3	4 hours
3	52	25	13	6	3	6 hours
4	53	25	13	6	3	8 ocloc'k

Based on the results obtained, it was established that the effective extraction of raw materials is the extraction of 1,2,3,4-plums for 6 hours and 5-plums for 4 hours.

Acute toxicity of the sum of water-soluble polysaccharides isolated from the root of the plant *Capparis spinosa* under administration to experimental animals at a dose of 1000.0-2000.0-3000.0-4000.0-5000.0 mg/kg into the stomach through the oral cavity using an atraumatic probe, after 10-15 minutes motor activity was significantly weakened, hiccups appeared, there were no significant changes in breathing, heartbeat, perception of external sounds and pain compared to animals in the control group, the animals recovered within 60-80 minutes, and no mortality was observed within 24 hours. At a dose of 6000.0-7000.0-8000.0 mg/kg, movement slowed down after 5-8 minutes, the perception of pain and external sounds decreased slightly,

mortality was not observed within 24 hours, the animals returned to their original state after 2 days. In animals injected with 8500.0 mg/kg, motor activity slowed down after 4-6 minutes, hiccups, half-closed eyes, and mild tremor were observed, death was observed in 1 mouse after 47 minutes, death in 2 mice after 61 minutes. No mortality was observed in the remaining experimental animals during the day. At a dose of 8750.0 mg/kg, after 3-5 minutes, movement slowed down, breathing slowed down, hiccups and head tremor were observed, a motionless lying position on the stomach with relaxed muscles of the arms and legs was observed, the death of 1 mouse out of 6 animals was observed after 35 minutes, death in 2 - mice after 45 minutes, 3 mice after 63 minutes. No mortality was observed in the remaining experimental animals during the day. When a 9000.0 mg/kg dose of the substance

was administered, after 3-5 minutes there was a slowdown in movement, half-closed eyes, loss of external sound and pain perception, all animals had a prolonged tremor, relaxation of the muscles of the arms and legs, a lateral position, the death of the 1st mouse was observed after 21 minutes, the death of the 2nd after 32 minutes, the death of the 3rd mouse after 43 minutes, the death of the 4th mouse after 74 minutes. No death

was observed in the remaining experimental animals within 24 hours. When the substance was administered at a dose of 10,000.0 mg/kg, after 3-4 minutes there was a slowdown in movement, disappearance of pain and perception of external noise, relaxation of the muscles of the limbs, prolonged tremor, mortality in 100% of experimental animals 11-52 minutes, the results of the experiment are presented in the Table 4.

Table 4

Acute toxicity of the sum of polysaccharides isolated from the root of the *Capparis spinosa* plant.

No.	Drug name	Animal species	Method of administration	Dose, mg/kg	Mortality/ animal survival
1	Sum of polysaccharides isolated from the root of the plant <i>Capparis spinosa</i> .	Mice	Orally into the stomach	1000.0	0/6
				2000.0	0/6
				3000.0	0/6
				4000.0	0/6
				5000.0	0/6
				6000.0	0.6
				7000.0	0/6
				8000.0	0/6
				8500.0	2/4
				8750.0	3/3
				9000.0	4/2
10000.0	6/0				
LD ₅₀		8766.2 (8063.9-9978.4)			
LD ₁₀₀		12651.1			

Statistical analysis of the obtained data was performed using IBM® SPSS® Statistics v27.0.1.0 software:

Доверительные границы							
	95% доверительные границы для <i>Capparis spinosa</i>				95% доверительные границы для log (<i>Capparis spinosa</i>) ^a		
	Вероятность	Оценка	Нижняя граница	Верхняя граница	Оценка	Нижняя граница	Верхняя граница
PROBIT	,010	6074,229	2623,453	7077,401	3,783	3,419	3,850
	,020	6341,031	3033,399	7268,493	3,802	3,482	3,861
	,030	6516,353	3325,355	7394,081	3,814	3,522	3,869
	,040	6651,428	3562,806	7491,146	3,823	3,552	3,875
	,050	6763,364	3767,942	7571,972	3,830	3,576	3,879
	,060	6860,122	3951,408	7642,259	3,836	3,597	3,883
	,070	6946,097	4119,217	7705,153	3,842	3,615	3,887
	,080	7023,992	4275,133	7762,587	3,847	3,631	3,890
	,090	7095,593	4421,683	7815,843	3,851	3,646	3,893
	,100	7162,146	4560,651	7865,824	3,855	3,659	3,896
	,150	7444,404	5178,326	8085,098	3,872	3,714	3,908
	,200	7676,645	5717,151	8279,934	3,885	3,757	3,918
	,250	7881,653	6208,749	8471,425	3,897	3,793	3,928
	,300	8070,419	6664,399	8675,371	3,907	3,824	3,938
	,350	8249,371	7084,528	8908,668	3,916	3,850	3,950
	,400	8422,848	7462,436	9191,199	3,925	3,873	3,963
	,450	8594,159	7789,666	9543,095	3,934	3,892	3,980
	,500	8766,156	8063,984	9978,369	3,943	3,907	3,999
	,550	8941,596	8292,965	10502,688	3,951	3,919	4,021
	,600	9123,458	8489,562	11119,374	3,960	3,929	4,046
	,650	9315,316	8666,483	11837,278	3,969	3,938	4,073
	,700	9521,872	8834,239	12676,524	3,979	3,946	4,103
	,750	9749,921	9001,829	13674,992	3,989	3,954	4,136
	,800	10010,297	9178,535	14901,791	4,000	3,963	4,173
	,850	10322,586	9377,041	16492,174	4,014	3,972	4,217
	,900	10729,395	9621,283	18759,205	4,031	3,983	4,273
	,910	10830,032	9679,857	19354,681	4,035	3,986	4,287
	,920	10940,430	9743,421	20024,000	4,039	3,989	4,302
	,930	11063,118	9813,283	20787,783	4,044	3,992	4,318
	,940	11201,769	9891,337	21676,531	4,049	3,995	4,336
	,950	11362,023	9980,477	22738,083	4,055	3,999	4,357
	,960	11553,233	10085,471	24053,689	4,063	4,004	4,381
	,970	11792,716	10215,097	25778,267	4,072	4,009	4,411
	,980	12118,770	10388,613	28267,471	4,083	4,017	4,451
	,990	12651,070	10665,550	32695,509	4,102	4,028	4,514

а. Основание логарифма = 10.

The average lethal dose of the sum of polysaccharides isolated from the root of the *Capparis spinosa* plant (with a confidence interval of LD₅₀) is 8766.2 (8063.9–9978.4) mg/kg. According to GOST No. 12.1.007-76 the substance is on the list fewer toxic substances (class IV), and according to the classification of A.V. Stefanova is included in the list of substances with low practical toxicity (class V) [4].

Conclusion. Based on the above experiments, to extract the amount of water-soluble polysaccharides from caper root, it is necessary to grind the raw material to a size of 4-7 mm, use an aqueous solvent as a solvent, and also extract 5 times at a temperature of at least 60°C and 1,2,3,4- It is advisable to extract plums for 6 hours, and 5-plums for 4 hours. As a result of scientific research, it has been established that water-soluble polysaccha-

rides can be extracted from the root of the *Capparis spinosa* plant, containing 0.6% water-soluble polysaccharides, with a yield of at least 95%.

The inclusion of the sum of polysaccharides isolated from the root of *Capparis spinosa* into the group of substances with low acute toxicity provides the basis for further in-depth pharmacological studies of the biological activity of this substance.

References:

1. Aghel N.; Rashidi I. and Mombeini A. Hepatoprotective Activity of *Capparis spinosa* Root Bark Against CCl₄ Induced Hepatic Damage in Mice // Iranian Journal of Pharmaceutical Research. -2007. -6(4). -P. 285-290.
2. Ali-Shtayeh A., Abu Ghdeib S.L. Antifungal activity of plant extracts against dermatophytes // Mycoses. -1999. -№42. -P. 665-672.

3. Ambali S.F., Akanbi D.O., Oladipo O.O., Yaqub L.S., Kawu M.U. Subchronic Chlorpyrifos-Induced Clinical, Hematological and Biochemical Changes in Swiss Albino Mice: Protective Effect of Vitamin E // *Int. J. Biol. Med. Res.* -2011. -2(2): -P. 497-503.
4. Arrar L., Benzidane N., Krache I., Charef N., Khennouf S., Baghiani B. Comparison between polyphenol contents and antioxidant activities of different parts of *Capparis spinosa* L // *Phcog Commn.* -2013. -3.2. -P. 70-74.
5. Benzidane N., Charef N., Krache I., Baghianl A., Arrar L. In Vitro Bronchorelaxant Effects of *Capparis Spinosa* Aqueous Extracts on Rat Trachea // *J. App. Pharm. Sci.* -2013. -3.09. -P. 085-088.
6. Bonina F., Puglia C., Ventura D., Aquino R., Tortora S., Sacchi A., Saija A. Tomanio A., Pellegrino M.L., De Carparis P. In vitro antioxidant and in vivo photoprotective effects of a lyophilized extract of *Capparis spinosa* L. buds // *J. of Cosmetic Science.* -2002. -№53. -P. 321-335.
7. Cao Y.L., Li X., Zheng M. Effect of *Capparis spinosa* on fibroblast proliferation and type I collagen production in progressive systemic sclerosis // *Zhongguo Zhong Yao ZaZhi.* -2008. -33.5. -P. 560-563.
8. Eddouks M., Lemhadri A., Michel J. Hypolipidemic activity of aqueous extract of *Capparis spinosa* L. in normal and diabetic rats // *J. Ethanopharmacol.* -2005. -98.3. -P. 345-350.
9. Kulisic-Bilusic T., Schmoller K., Schnabele K., Siracusa L., Ruberto G. The anticarcinogenic potential of essential oil and aqueous infusion from caper (*Capparis spinosa* L.) // *Food Chemistry.* 2012. -№132. -P. 261–267.
10. Panico A.M., Cardile V., Garufi F., Puglia C., Bonina F., Ronsisvalle G. / Protective effect of *C.spinosa* on chondrocytes // *Life. Sci.* -2005. -№20. -P. 2479-88.
11. Yilli A., Tao Wu, Сагдуллаев Б.Т., Aisa H.A., Ульченко Н.Т., Глушенкова А.И., Рахмонбердиева Р.К. Липиды и углеводы корней *Capparis spinosa* // *Хим.природ.соед.* -2006. -№1. -С. 81-82.
12. Asilbekova D.T., Tursunkhodjaeva F.M., Yuldasheva N.K., Ul'chenko N.T., Glushenkova A.I. Lipids from seeds and leaves of *Capparis spinosa* L. // 7th International Symposium on the Chemistry of Natural Compounds, Tashkent. -2007. -P. 116.
13. Юлдашева Н.К., Ульченко Н.Т., Глушенкова А.И. Липиды семян *Capparis spinosa* // *Хим.природ.соед.* -2008. -№ 5. -С. 516.
14. Асилбекова Д.Т., Турсунходжаева Ф.М. Липиды листьев *Capparis spinosa* L. // *Химия растительного сырья.* -2009. -№2 -С. 97-99.
15. Халматов Х.Х. Дикорастущие лекарственные растения Узбекистана // *Ташкент. Медицина.* -1964. -185 с.
16. Акопов И.Э. Кровоостанавливающие растения // *Ташкент. "Медицина"* -1981. -295.с.
17. <http://doctors.am/en>.
18. European Convention for the Protection of Vertebrate Animals Used for Experimental and Other Scientific Purposes, ETS №123, Strasbourg. 1986.
19. Руководство по проведению доклинических исследований лекарственных средств. Часть первая / Председатель редакционной коллегии А.Н. Миронов. – М.: Гриф и К, 2012. – 944с.
20. Бельский М.Л. «Элементы количественной оценки фармакологического эффекта», Мендиз Ленинград.1963, с. 146.